

Care of Severely Mentally ill: Where We Are

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The beginning of the Community Mental Health program in the 1960s in the U.S., led to the de-institutionalization of mental health care and is known as the era of emergence of Psychosocial Rehabilitation of persons who have a severe mental illness (SMI). In mid-1970s in India, the first community mental health unit was set up at the National Institute of Mental Health and Neuro Sciences (NIMHANS) with rural mental health center provision at Sakalwara, Bangalore Rural District. In addition to extending services in the rural locality, many professionals working in the field of mental health were trained at this center.

Subsequently, the National Mental Health Programme (NMHP) was launched in the early 1980s at Raipur Rani to integrate mental health care with the Primary Health Care centres. All these service models proved beneficial but could not be expanded due to some reason or the other, even after realizing that they were replicable service models elsewhere in the country and beneficial to the community.

Before the beginning of the Community Mental Health Movement in the U.S., during the 1950s, Dr. Vidya Sagar at Rohtak, Haryana involved families in treating persons with severe mental illness. This initiative proved helpful in reducing hostility and criticality towards family members and minimizing stigma during those early years in the post-independence era (Kapur 1992). This development paved the way for community care of persons with severe mental illness in India, signifying that only drugs are insufficient for managing these cases in a comprehensive manner.

The voluntary community care efforts through NGOs also played a significant role in expanding mental health services through their service delivery initiatives and awareness programs. A few known among all them are SCARFF (Chennai), SNEHA (Chennai), Richmond Fellowship Foundation (Bangalore and New Delhi), CADABAMS (Bangalore). Dr. Sharda Menon is also a well-known name in setting up the management and care of persons with severe mental illness.

Shifting mental health care from mental hospitals to psychiatry departments of general hospitals during the

early 1970s was a significant development in severe mental illness care where this population drew sufficient attention from mental health professionals. A realization had gone into the mind of service providers about this population when they described the group as "the forgotten millions" Agrawal (1998), "The neglected lot" (Kulhara, 1997), with a lucid description of their life in the family and the kind of treatment they are getting.

There had been well-described observations available about the magnitude of the problem (Kulhara, 1997; Reddy & Chandrashekar, 1998; Ganguli, 2000). These findings suggest that 1 - 2% of people have a severe mental illness at any given point of time, and 0.5% to 1% of people go through disabling conditions on account of severe mental illness. The majority of this population is living in rural areas. Thus, extending services in the community remains always a significant challenge in the coming years.

District Mental Health Programme (DMHP) of MOH&FW: The government of India has facilitated the manpower development and expansion of services in rural areas. Community care has always been proved to be financially viable, ensures availability of benefits of non-institutional quality care to a larger population.

The emergence of various approaches to help this population on a temporal continuum; like skill training supplemented with the token economy, social skills learning through modelling, application of cognitive methods into skill training promoting living and social skills, and video modelling are strategies are well known.

Now a good number of Clinical Psychologists are employed under DMHP. Their observations are of utmost importance given the psychosocial care in the community, categorically stated by Gopinath & Rao (1994). Currently, few priorities in terms of care by clinical psychologists are ensuring integration of persons with SMI into their families by offering psychoeducation, promoting living skills, social interaction strategies, and relapse prevention techniques remain to be achieved for the larger population in the community. These interventions have been documented to be beneficial by minimizing

the caregiver burden and expressed emotions. In addition, the efforts are to be focused more towards prevention in nature, in conjunction with functional assessment, disability certification and availability of rehabilitation services. Recently, local adaptations are also being discussed to ensure continuity of care, support for psychoeducation, provision for welfare benefits, and access to meaningful social activities (Tirthali, 2020).

Integration of mental health care into primary health care is the felt need of the time. Still, at the same time, integration of these services into community based rehabilitation has also been talked about in the welfare sector by MOSJ&E: Government of India (Raja et al., 2008). Regional rehabilitation centres, district rehabilitation centres and provision of rehabilitation camps are some of the existing programs under this Ministry. As per the Persons with Disabilities Act (PWD) provisions, these centres are committed to extending mental health services to persons with severe mental illness in the community.

Keeping in view the urgent need for an apex institute in this service area, Government of India under MOSJ&E established (in 2019), National Institute of Mental Health Rehabilitation near Bhopal in Madhya Pradesh. The defined objectives of NIMHR are service delivery, development of replicable service models, manpower development, research and community oriented services. Currently available resources show that early efforts of setting up community mental health services in Sakalwara, Bangalore Rural District or Raipur Rani in Punjab

were proved fruitful in the recent past with a lot of psychological awareness evolving in the community and a ray of hope among the working professionals and family members who offer care to persons with severe mental illness.

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